

THE PURPOSE OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

ABSTRACT

The article is concerned with the study of the purpose of discourse analysis. Discourse analysis has provided models and methods of engaging issues that emanate from disciplines such as education, cultural studies, communication and so. The study focuses on the materials for analyzing, the aim of conducting discourse and what is analyzed within the discourse.

Previous researches and studies in this area of investigation have been gathered and analyzed. Several points of the issue have been taken into consideration and concluded that the main purpose of discourse analysis is identifying the contextual meaning of language in different spheres of communication.

KEY WORDS: Discourse, Discourse analysis, Materials, Vocabulary, Grammar, Structure, Genre, Non-Verbal Communication, Conversational Code.

INTRODUCTION

Discourse analysis is usually defined as a broad field which can include the theories and methods of linguistics, sociology, philosophy and psychology. When it comes to define what discourse analysis is, it is important to point out the background of this theory. In simple terms, Discourse analysis uses the language presented in a corpus or body of data **to draw meaning**. This body of data could include a set of interviews or focus group discussion transcripts. While some forms of discourse analysis centre in on the specifics of language (such as sounds or grammar), other forms focus on *how* **this language is used** to achieve its aims

The term discourse analysis was first used by the sentence linguist, Zellig Harris in his 1952 article entitled "Discourse Analysis". He defined this term as a method for analysis of connected speech or writing for continuing descriptive linguistics beyond the limit of a

simple sentence at a time.³ However, the definition of discourse analysis has still been under the discussion. According to Brown and Yule, discourse can be the analysis of language in use. The term language in use means the set of norms, preferences and expectations which relate language in context.

Guy Cook describes that: “discourse is seen as a language in use or language used to communicate something felt to be coherent which may or may not correspond to a correct sentence or series of correct sentences⁴. Similarly, Stubbs perceives discourse analysis as a “conglomeration of attempts to study the organization of language and therefore, to study larger linguistic units, such as conversational exchanges or written text. As Wodak and Krzyżanowski (2008) put it: “discourse analysis provides a general framework to problem-oriented social research”. Basically, discourse analysis is used to conduct research on **the use of language in context** in a wide variety of social problems (i.e., issues in society that affect individuals negatively).⁵

MATERIALS AND PURPOSE OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

In this article, we are going to point out the materials and purpose of discourse analysis. Many linguists claim that the main purpose of conducting discourse analysis is examining how language functions and how meaning is created in different social contexts. It can be applied to any instance of written or oral language, as well as non-verbal aspects of communication such as tone and gestures.

Materials that are suitable for discourse analysis include:

³ Harris, Z. (1952). ‘Discourse Analysis.’ *Language*, 28, 1-30.

2. Cook, G (1989). *Discourse*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁵ Wodak, R. (1995). ‘Critical Linguistics and Critical Discourse Analysis.’ *Handbook of Pragmatics: Manual*. Eds. Verschueren, J. et al. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. pp 204-210

- Books, newspapers and periodicals
- Marketing material, such as brochures and advertisements
- Business and government documents
- Websites, forums, social media posts and comments
- Interviews and conversations

By analyzing these types of discourse, researchers aim to gain an understanding of social groups and how they communicate.

Discourse analysis investigates the contextual meaning of language whilst other linguistic approaches emphasize only the rule of language usage. Particularly, this analysis aims to do research on how people use language to achieve specific effects.⁶ Additionally, in discourse analysis, large chunks of language are investigated, such as texts, entire communication, stories.

The table illustrates how selected materials are analyzed:

Vocabulary	Words and phrases can be analyzed for ideological associations, formality, and euphemistic and metaphorical content.
Grammar	The way that sentences are constructed (e.g. verb tenses, active or passive construction, and the use of imperatives and questions) can reveal aspects of intended meaning.
Structure	The structure of a text can be analyzed for how it creates emphasis or builds a narrative.
Genre	Texts can be analyzed in relation to the conventions and communicative aims of their genre (e.g. political speeches or tabloid newspaper articles).

⁶ [Amy Luo. \(2019\). Discourse Analysis | A Step-by-Step Guide with Examples](#)

Non-verbal communication	Non-verbal aspects of speech, such as tone of voice, pauses, gestures, and sounds like “um”, can reveal aspects of a speaker’s intentions, attitudes, and emotions.
Conversational code	The interaction between people in a conversation, such as turn-taking, interruptions and listener response, can reveal aspects of cultural conventions and social roles.

CONCLUSION

We have tried in this article to discuss aspects of discourse analysis we consider fundamental to the study and analysis of discourse. We attempted to define the concept of discourse, the materials and purpose to analysis of discourse. Further, we discussed how selected source can be analyzed. As we noted in the introductory part of the article, Discourse Analysis is a vast discipline and insights from it have been used in solving problems that originate from so many other disciplines and domains of study.

REFERENCES:

1. [Amy Luo. \(2019\). Discourse Analysis | A Step-by-Step Guide with Examples](#)
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